

INTERNATIONAL ASTRONOMICAL UNION
COLLOQUIUM No. 48
Vienna, September 12–14, 1978

MODERN ASTROMETRY

Edited by
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Published by
UNIVERSITY OBSERVATORY VIENNA

SEPARATUM

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Herausgeber und Verleger:

Institut für Astronomie (Universitäts-Sternwarte Wien)

PHOTOELECTRIC ASTROMETRY
A COMPARISON OF METHODS FOR PRECISE IMAGE LOCATION

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ABSTRACT

Several techniques for obtaining the precise location of a noisy image (of a star, spectral line, solar limb, etc.) are described by means of characteristic "weighting functions". The imprecision of an image location estimate can be expressed in terms of the weighting function and the image shape and noise covariance. It is limited by the intrinsic imprecision of the image, which is attained with an optimum weighting function, computable from the image characteristics. The hypothetical optimum method is compared with some commonly used location methods, such as computing the median or centre of gravity, least-squares fitting and cross correlating, and hardware techniques including the quadrant detector and rotating knife-edge. One- and two-dimensional Gaussian images are considered as well as diffraction and seeing images. The general results apply also to photographic astrometry, measurement of radial velocities, timing of pulses, etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are numerous situations in astrometry and other branches of observational astronomy when it is required to determine very precisely the position of a noisy image or feature of approximately known shape and size. To take a few examples: (1) The output signal of the photoelectric slit micrometer is a current or sequence of photoelectron counts containing a number of humps corresponding to the moments when the star image crosses the slits. The precise time of each hump is required. (2) A fundamental step in photographic astrometry consists in measuring accurately the plate coordinates of a number of diffuse and grainy photographic star images. (3) To find the linear coordinates of photographically recorded spectral lines presents a similar problem in radial-velocity work. (4) To measure the solar diameter, photoelectric scans may be obtained normally to the limbs. The positions of the limbs are then derived by some numerical processing of the scans.

These are examples of what we might call the image location problem. The word "image" then denotes any kind of local feature, the precise location of which is wanted: a hump in a curve or record of numbers, a real or photographic star image, a spectral line, a limb. The "location" is its

one- or two-dimensional coordinate in space or time, or the process of finding it. The location may be referred to a casual or instrumental coordinate system; its subsequent calibration (transformation to celestial coordinates, wavelengths, etc.) is a completely different matter with which we are not concerned in this paper.

A multitude of automated techniques have been developed for image location purposes. The present paper is an attempt to "parametrize" a number of such methods and describe their interaction with images by a simple mathematical model. The approach is to regard the image location process as a "black box", the input being the noisy image, the output an estimate of its location. We are not much interested in the detailed physical or numerical implementation of the location process, but try to represent the resulting input/output relations by a small set of parameters (the weighting function). Vastly different techniques, e.g. a star tracker employing a servo-controlled quadrant detector, or a television system with a computer analyzing the camera signal, may in principle have identical input/output relations and are then equivalent from our point of view. There are two important advantages of such an approach. Firstly, it allows a wide variety of techniques to be described uniformly and in simple terms, thus emphasizing fundamental similarities and differences between different techniques and facilitating quantitative comparisons. Secondly, the parametrized location model can be optimized, i.e. its parameters may be chosen to minimize the expected imprecision of the estimated locations of images of a certain kind. The optimum method may then serve as an absolute standard for judging the merits of various sub-optimal techniques.

In the following section we formulate a simple image model and define the image location process in terms of a weighting function. In Section 3 an expression is derived for the imprecision of the location estimate, and this is then minimized (Section 4) to yield the intrinsic imprecision of the image. Examples of weighting functions are given in Section 5. The last two sections contain a numerical comparison of certain image location techniques and a discussion of their relative merits in different situations.

2. MODELS OF THE IMAGE AND LOCATION PROCESS

We shall adopt the simplest possible image model, depending on one free parameter only, the location. The observed quantity $s(t)$ is statistically described by a location parameter τ and two known functions, f , the average

image profile, and C , the noise covariance function:

$$\begin{aligned} s(t) &= f(t-\tau) + e(t) \\ E[e(t)] &= 0 \\ E[e(t_1)e(t_2)] &= C(t_1-\tau, t_2-\tau), \quad t_1, t_2 \in T. \end{aligned} \quad (1a)$$

The argument t and location parameter τ may be one- or two-dimensional, in the latter case often denoted $\vec{t}$ and $\vec{\tau}$. $e(t)$ is additive noise having zero mean; E is the expectation operator and T the region of t being observed.

The image location problem consists in estimating τ , when the functions f , C , and s are given.

The function s is very often sampled in a finite and regular set of points, in which case we use the model

$$\begin{aligned} s_i &= f(t_i-\tau) + e_i \\ E(e_i) &= 0 \\ E(e_i e_j) &= C(t_i-\tau, t_j-\tau), \quad t_i, t_j \in T, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned} \quad (1b)$$

Note that f and C remain the same and continuous.

Except for the solar limb observations, the examples quoted in the Introduction all have images consisting of local humps or depressions in an otherwise nearly constant background or continuum. For the analysis in the next two sections this is in fact assumed; moreover, we assume that the observed region T is large enough to accommodate the entire feature of interest. Thus,

$$f(T_1-\tau) \simeq f(T_2-\tau) \quad (2)$$

if T_1 and T_2 are the extreme points of T (or, in the two-dimensional case, any two points on the border of T).

The image location process is an analysis of the image (by hardware or software) resulting in an estimate of τ . It is necessary to distinguish from here on between the true location, which we denote τ_0 , and the estimate thereof, denoted $\hat{\tau}$. We shall deal with a particular type of location estimator, for which $\hat{\tau}$ satisfies an equation of the form

$$g(\hat{\tau}) \equiv \int_T s(t) w(t-\hat{\tau}) dt = 0 \quad (3a)$$

or, in the discrete case,

$$g(\hat{\tau}) \equiv \sum_i s_i w(t_i-\hat{\tau}) = 0. \quad (3b)$$

In either case w is a continuous *weighting function* characterizing the

estimator. If t is a vector there must be one equation like (3) for each dimension, simultaneously satisfied.

3. PROPERTIES OF THE LOCATION ESTIMATOR

We shall examine the first- and second-order statistics of $\hat{\tau}$, as defined by (3a). For mathematical convenience we prefer to work with the continuous case [eqs. (1a) and (3a)], and assume that similar results hold for the discrete case if integrals are replaced by sums, etc.

Making a Taylor expansion of $g(\tau)$ around the true location τ_0 and reversing the series, we find to first order

$$\hat{\tau} - \tau_0 = [g(\hat{\tau}) - g(\tau_0)]/g'(\tau_0) - \dots, \quad (4)$$

where the prime (') denotes a derivative (partial if t is a vector). By taking the expectation of (4), while using that $g(\hat{\tau}) = 0$ and some obvious first-order approximations, it is found that the condition for unbiasedness, $E(\hat{\tau} - \tau_0) = 0$, becomes simply

$$\int f(t) w(t) dt = 0. \quad (5)$$

We shall assume that (5) is always fulfilled.

Squaring eq. (4) and taking the expectation we find in a similar way the mean square error of $\hat{\tau}$, $E[(\hat{\tau} - \tau_0)^2]$; for the unbiased estimate this equals the *variance*

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\iint C(t_1, t_2) w(t_1) w(t_2) dt_1 dt_2}{[\int f'(t) w(t) dt]^2}. \quad (6)$$

4. OPTIMUM ESTIMATOR AND THE INTRINSIC IMPRECISION

By means of Cauchy-Schwarz' inequality it can be shown that the right member of (6) is minimized by a weighting function $\bar{w}$ satisfying the equation

$$\int C(t_1, t_2) \bar{w}(t_2) dt_2 = f'(t_1), \quad (7)$$

or by any non-zero multiple of $\bar{w}$. Eq. (7) defines the *optimum weighting function*; the corresponding mean error $\bar{\sigma}$ may be called the *intrinsic imprecision* of the image. It is given by the equations

$$\bar{\sigma}^{-2} = \int f'(t) \bar{w}(t) dt = \iint C(t_1, t_2) \bar{w}(t_1) \bar{w}(t_2) dt_1 dt_2. \quad (8)$$

Eq. (7) must in general be solved numerically after discretization. There are however at least two practically important cases for which an analytical solution of (7) and subsequent evaluation of (8) are readily

obtained, viz. for Poissonian noise and constant-power white noise.

The covariance function of Poissonian noise is

$$C(t_1, t_2) = f(t_1) \delta(t_1 - t_2) \quad (9)$$

(δ being the Dirac function), provided that $f \geq 0$ is expressed as the expected rate of events per unit interval of t . The optimum weighting function obtained by solving eq. (7) is

$$\bar{w}(t) = f'(t)/f(t), \quad (10)$$

and the intrinsic imprecision of the Poisson process is

$$\bar{\sigma} = \left[\int [f'(t)]^2 \frac{dt}{f(t)} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (11)$$

For white noise of constant total power (variance) P , the covariance function, optimum weighting function, and intrinsic imprecision are:

$$C(t_1, t_2) = P \delta(t_1 - t_2), \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{w}(t) = P^{-1} f'(t), \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{\sigma} = P^{1/2} \left[\int [f'(t)]^2 dt \right]^{-1/2} \quad (14)$$

5. EXAMPLES OF WEIGHTING FUNCTIONS

A number of widely different image location methods will be described in this section by means of weighting functions. Most of the common location methods employed in astrometry do in fact rely on the use of weighting functions, although this is often implicit and far from obvious, as shown by some of the examples below. There are however important techniques which cannot be described by a simple convolutional equation like (3a); these include in particular methods using frequency modulation for encoding the image location. An example is the Astrometric Multiplexing Area Scanner⁽¹⁾ and similar devices, which are consequently not further discussed.

Another limitation to the present description of location estimators is related to the image model adopted, eqs. (1a) or (1b). This assumes a time-independent noise pattern $e(t)$ or $\{e_i\}$. With some modulating devices it happens however that the noise pattern is changing *during the location process itself*, e.g. the rotating knife-edge or Connes' modulator operating in the photoelectron-noise limited mode. While the present model correctly predicts the average location obtained in such cases, it fails to represent

the statistical effects of the constantly changing noise. In other words: solution of eq. (3a) requires that the *same* realization of the noise is available for *different* trial locations $\vec{r}$. Eq. (6) for the variance of the location estimate, and all equations in Section 4, are valid only if the time constant of the changing noise pattern is much longer than the time constant of the location process. For a rotating knife-edge this condition is certainly met when centering on photographic images, and possibly for real-time centering on the seeing image of a bright star (if the time constant of the device is less than a few tens of milliseconds), but it is definitely not fulfilled if photoelectron noise dominates. A detailed analysis of the last case shows that the rotating knife-edge (with cosine demodulation) gives exactly twice the mean error of the quadrant detector having identical size and quantum efficiency. This loss by a factor four in the effective number of photoelectrons is understandable since the rotating knife-edge always obscures half the image and spends half the time measuring the other coordinate. For this particular device we thus have to distinguish between the cases of "constant" and "variable" noise (Table 1).

5.1. The mean (centre of gravity)

The mean or centre of gravity of t , weighted by $s(t)$ or s_i , is clearly obtained with the weighting function

$$w(t) = ct, \quad (15)$$

where c is a constant different from zero. For a Poisson process, eq. (9), the area-normalized function f (if it exists) can be regarded as a probability density function, and (15) then defines the sample mean. This is known to be the optimum location estimator for a normal distribution, $f(t) = \exp(-t^2/2s^2)/(\sqrt{2\pi}s)$. This can be seen by computing the optimum weighting function from (10), $\bar{w}(t) = -t/s^2$. [Note that (11) gives $\bar{\sigma} = s$.] But it is well known that the sample mean is very sensitive to deviations from normality in the tails of the probability density function, i.e. to outliers. One often tries to get a more robust estimate by weighting observations differently according to their deviations from a provisional mean. Throwing away points beyond a distance a from the final mean corresponds to using a weighting function of the form

$$w(t) = \begin{cases} ct & \text{for } |t| < a \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

This defines the *trimmed mean* (Figs. 1c and 2a). Other methods for robust

estimation of the location of a contaminated normal distribution are discussed e.g. by Huber.⁽²⁾ In this context the estimators defined by (3a) are equivalent to Huber's M-estimators.

5.2. The median

The trimmed median of half-width a is defined by the weighting function

$$w(t) = \begin{cases} ct/|t| & \text{for } |t| < a \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

(Figs. 1d and 2b). The two-dimensional trimmed median is mechanically implemented by quadrant detectors and image-bisecting star trackers, and by the Pulkovo photoelectric micrometer⁽³⁾ using a reflecting grid and two photomultipliers. The output of the photoelectric multislit micrometer is digitally analyzed, using the trimmed median, to yield the transit times at the slits.^(4, 5)

5.3. Least-squares fit and cross-correlation techniques

The unweighted least-squares fit of $f(t-\tau)$ to $s(t)$ minimizes the quadratic loss function $\mathcal{L}(\tau) \equiv \int [s(t) - f(t-\tau)]^2 dt$. Under assumption (2) the condition $(\partial/\partial\tau)\mathcal{L}(\hat{\tau}) = 0$ takes the form of (3a) with weighting function

$$w(t) = f'(t) \quad (18)$$

(Figs. 1a and 2d). It is worth noting that application of the trimmed mean and median, eqs. (16) and (17), is tantamount to least-squares fitting the apex of a parabola and triangle, respectively.

Eq. (13) shows that least-squares methods are in fact optimal in cases with white (i.e. uncorrelated) constant-power noise. Their usefulness is well-known to astrometrists (who sometimes even tend to put too much faith in them). For instance, it has been found that photographic star images are conveniently and accurately located by fitting Gaussian functions to density profiles obtained with a scanning microdensitometer.^(6, 7)

Very closely related are the cross-correlation techniques. The condition for maximum correlation between a given model function $h(t)$ and the observed function $s(t)$, $\int s(t) h(t-\hat{\tau}) dt = \text{maximum}$, gives upon derivation an equation like (3a) with $w(t) = h'(t)$. Cross correlation is however easier to implement by hardware than least-squares fitting, e.g. the photoelectric radial-velocity spectrometer⁽⁸⁾ and its astrometric counterpart, the photoelectric parallax scanner.⁽⁹⁾ Digital techniques for cross-corre-

Figure 1. Examples of one-dimensional weighting functions to be used for locating the Gaussian "image" shown at top left. They represent: (a) a least-squares fit; (b) the optimum estimator (for Poissonian noise); (c) the trimmed mean (cut-off distance a); (d) the trimmed median.

Figure 2. Two-dimensional weighting functions for locating the Gaussian image at top left. (a) the trimmed mean; (b) the trimmed median (e.g. a quadrant detector); (c) the rotating knife-edge with cosine demodulation; (d) a least-squares fit. The weighting functions shown here determine the x coordinate only; for the other coordinate there is a similar set of functions obtained by rotation through 90° .

lating stellar spectra for determination of Doppler and Zeeman shifts are well established.⁽¹⁰⁻¹³⁾ Da Costa *et al.*⁽¹¹⁾ perform the cross correlation in the Fourier domain, and apply at the same time a band-pass filter to remove low-frequency trends and high-frequency noise. This is equivalent to filtering the digital spectrum before cross correlating, which in turn is equivalent to filtering the weighting function before applying eq. (3a), i.e. to using a slightly modified weighting function.

5.4. Maximum likelihood estimator for a Poisson process

Let the pulse train $s(t) \equiv \sum_j \delta(t - \theta_j)$ be a Poisson process with events at coordinates $\theta_j \in T$ and intensity (i.e. expected rate of events) $f(t - \tau_0)$. The likelihood function (logarithm of probability of observing $s(t)$ given the location τ) is⁽¹⁴⁾

$$L(\tau) \equiv - \int f(t - \tau) dt + \int \ln[f(t - \tau)] s(t) dt. \quad (19)$$

Again using assumption (2) we find that the condition for maximum likelihood reduces to an equation like (3a) with

$$w(t) = f'(t)/f(t). \quad (20)$$

For Poissonian noise the optimum weighting function, eq. (10), thus gives us the maximum likelihood estimate of τ_0 .

5.5. The rotating knife-edge

The rotating knife-edge was introduced by Babcock in the late forties for automatic telescope guiding.⁽¹⁵⁾ It has then been successfully used for centering on photographic star images⁽¹⁶⁾ and as a star tracker in the Bordeaux photoelectric micrometer.⁽¹⁷⁾ A semi-circular aperture is rotating in the image plane around an axis at the centre of the circle. A photomultiplier measures the modulated intensity behind the aperture. Demodulation of the signal yields two error signals, one for each coordinate, which control the centering or tracking.

Suppose that the image $s(\vec{t}) \equiv s(t_x, t_y)$ remains constant during the response time of the device, i.e. for several revolutions of the knife-edge. Let $\vec{\tau} \equiv (\tau_x, \tau_y)$ be the centre of rotation and a and θ the radius and position angle of the aperture. The photomultiplier signal is then

$$i(\theta) = \int_0^a \rho d\rho \int_{\theta - \pi/2}^{\theta + \pi/2} s(\tau_x + \rho \cos \phi, \tau_y + \rho \sin \phi) d\phi. \quad (21)$$

Synchronous demodulation by means of a periodic function $p(\theta)$ produces the error signals

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_x(\vec{\tau}) &= \int_0^{2\pi} i(\theta) p(\theta) d\theta = \iint s(\vec{t}) w_x(\vec{t} - \vec{\tau}) d\vec{t}, \\ \epsilon_y(\vec{\tau}) &= \int_0^{2\pi} i(\theta) p(\theta - \frac{\pi}{2}) d\theta = \iint s(\vec{t}) w_y(\vec{t} - \vec{\tau}) d\vec{t},\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

which are zero when the centre of rotation is at $\hat{i}$. The two weighting functions are

$$\begin{aligned}w_x(t \cos \phi, t \sin \phi) &= \int_{\phi - \pi/2}^{\phi + \pi/2} p(\theta) d\theta, \\ w_y(t \cos \phi, t \sin \phi) &= \int_{\phi - \pi/2}^{\phi + \pi/2} p(\theta - \frac{\pi}{2}) d\theta\end{aligned}\quad (23)$$

for $0 \leq |\vec{t}| \leq a$, and $w_x = w_y = 0$ for $|\vec{t}| > a$. The demodulating function is usually a square-wave or a cosine function; w_x and w_y are then periodic triangle respectively trigonometric functions of ϕ (Fig. 2c).

5.6. Method proposed by P. Connes

Connes has proposed a new type of astrometric instrument^(18, 19) comprising a photoelectric device for measuring the motion and parallax of a star relative to the centre of gravity of the lights from a large number of surrounding faint stars. The background stars are observed through a mask, specially made for each field, with a suitable transmission pattern $T(\vec{t})$ approximately centred on each star. A circular motion of the mask modulates the total transmitted intensity falling on a photomultiplier tube; demodulation of the resulting current provides two error signals which control the centering of the mask motion. [The position of the central (program) star relative to the mask is obtained with a separate device which is not considered here.]

Consider a single background star image $s(\vec{t}) \equiv s(t_x, t_y)$. The centre of the transmission pattern T describes a circle $\vec{\tau} + \vec{r}(\theta)$, where $\vec{r}(\theta) = (r \cos \theta, r \sin \theta)$, around the point $\vec{\tau}$. The photocurrent is

$$i(\theta) = \iint s(\vec{t}) T[\vec{t} - \vec{r}(\theta) - \vec{\tau}] d\vec{t},\quad (24)$$

which after demodulation by means of $p(\theta)$ gives two error signals as in (22) but with weighting functions

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_x(\vec{t}) &= \int_0^{2\pi} T[\vec{t} - \vec{r}(\theta)] p(\theta) d\theta, \\
 w_y(\vec{t}) &= \int_0^{2\pi} T[\vec{t} - \vec{r}(\theta)] p(\theta - \frac{\pi}{2}) d\theta.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{25}$$

Connes suggests in particular a transmission pattern $T(t \cos \phi, t \sin \phi) = \cos^2 \phi$ and demodulating function $p(\theta) = \cos \theta$. Evaluation of (25) then shows that w_x and w_y are proportional to t_x and t_y , respectively, i.e. the position obtained is precisely the centre of gravity of the star image.

When evaluating the precision of this method it must be remembered that the weighting functions in (25) are relevant only if the noise pattern of the image is changing slowly enough. If photoelectron noise is the limiting factor we should expect the method to give at least twice the mean error of a two-dimensional photon-counting detector followed by an off-line computation of the photocentre, albeit the two methods employ exactly the same weighting functions.

5.7. Definition of the solar limb

Certain definitions of the solar limb are conveniently expressed in terms of weighting functions, although eq. (2) obviously does not hold in this case. Let $s(t)$ be the observed intensity at coordinate t normal to the limb. The location of the limb τ_0 is required. Unless one has a detailed model of the true limb darkening and atmospheric transfer function to fit to the observation, the limb definition is always to some extent arbitrary. For instance, one may use the point of inflection of $s(t)$ to define the limb,⁽²⁰⁾ which is equivalent to using the weighting function $w(t) = -\delta(t-a) + 2\delta(t) - \delta(t+a)$ (numerical differencing with a finite step size a must of course be assumed). This definition is obviously very sensitive to noise, particularly if a is small. That problem may be avoided by smoothing $s(t)$ before computing the point of inflection; this is equivalent to using a weighting function equal to the second derivative of the smoothing function.

The Finite Fourier Transform Definition of the solar limb⁽²¹⁾ is claimed to be less sensitive to variable seeing than the inflection-point definition. An interval $[\tau-a, \tau+a]$ of t near the limb is scanned by a sinusoidally oscillating slit. The photomultiplier signal is digitally Fourier transformed to yield an error signal

$$\varepsilon(\tau) = \int_{-1/2}^{+1/2} s(\tau + a \sin \pi x) \cos(2\pi x) dx \quad (26)$$

which is zero when the centre of the scanned interval is at $\hat{i}$, the estimated limb location. Changing to the new variable $t = \tau + a \sin(\pi x)$, an equation like (3a) results, with weighting function

$$w(t) = c (a^2 - 2t^2) (a^2 - t^2)^{-1/2}. \quad (27)$$

6. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The theory outlined in the previous sections will be used here to compare numerically some of the image location methods described in Section 5. Since the relative precisions of the various methods very much depend on the characteristics of the image, we shall regard five qualitatively different images. The first two are one-dimensional and consist of a Gaussian feature appearing in "emission" and "absorption" relative to a constant background intensity. The other three images are two-dimensional: a Gaussian plus background, the diffraction image of a star, and the frozen seeing image of a star. The noise is Poissonian except for the seeing image for which the atmospheric effects are supposed to dominate. The different images are accurately specified below; the numerical results are summarized in Table 1 and further discussed in Section 7.

6.1. One-dimensional Gaussian image

The average image profile is

$$f(t) = \frac{N}{\sqrt{2\pi}s} \{ k \pm \exp(-t^2/2s^2) \}. \quad (28)$$

The sign is positive for an emission feature, negative for an absorption feature. s is the standard width of the Gaussian and N the total number of events contained (or missing) in it (photoelectrons, grains, or equivalent). The parameter k sets the background level. The noise covariance function is (9).

This model may be applied to the output signal of the photoelectric slit micrometer for the faintest stars (when photoelectron noise dominates), and of course to various types of photoelectric spectral-line observations. It is also approximately valid for modelling photographic images of Gaussian shape, if $s(t)$ is the observed number density of photographic grains (which obeys Poisson statistics). This in turn is proportional to the ordinary photographic density measured from a zero-point with no plate in the

beam, (22) rather than relative to the chemical fog as is usually the practice.

The computation of σ and $\bar{\sigma}$ is straightforward. Table 1 lists results for an emission feature with $k = 1/9$ and an absorption feature with $k = 10/9$. In both cases the maximum-to-minimum ratio of $f(t)$ is 10.

6.2. Two-dimensional Gaussian image

With the same notations as in (28) the model now is

$$f(\vec{t}) = \frac{N}{2\pi s^2} (k + \exp(-t^2/2s^2)), \quad (29)$$

with eq. (9) for the noise. It may represent faint seeing images and the photographic density of unsaturated photographic star images, which have approximately Gaussian shape.^(6, 7) The intrinsic limitations of such images have been extensively investigated by Farrell.^(23, 24)

Table 1 gives numerical results for $k = 1/9$. It must be noted that the rotating knife-edge, when used for centering on photographic images, operates on the intensity of the light transmitted by the plate, and not on photographic density. Thus the mean error stated in Table 1 for the rotating knife-edge with constant noise pattern refers to the rather artificial case of eq. (23) being applied to an observed density distribution.

6.3. Diffraction image of a star

The precision of astrometric observations is ultimately limited by diffraction and photon statistics, i.e. by the manifestations of the double nature of light, as waves and particles. The two effects are combined in a remarkably simple formula for the intrinsic imprecision of the diffraction image, which is derived in the following (an alternative derivation is given by Falconi⁽²⁵⁾).

Let $\vec{t} = (t_x, t_y)$ be *angular* coordinates in the focal plane, with origin at the geometrical centre of the diffraction image intensity $f(\vec{t})$ (expressed in the expected number of photoelectrons per unit solid angle). $\vec{r} = (r_x, r_y)$ are the corresponding *linear* coordinates in the plane of the entrance pupil, with origin at the centre of gravity of the entrance pupil. The entrance pupil is defined by the pupil function $A(\vec{r})$, which is unity if $\vec{r}$ is within the pupil and zero otherwise. The Fraunhofer diffraction is

$$f(\vec{t}) = F \frac{k^2}{4\pi^2} \left| \iint A(\vec{r}) \exp(-ik \vec{t} \cdot \vec{r}) d\vec{r} \right|^2, \quad (30)$$

where F is the equivalent photon density (per unit area) in the entrance pupil and $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number. We are looking for the intrinsic imprecision in the x direction (say), $\bar{\sigma}_x$. Eq. (11) may be re-written

$$\bar{\sigma}_x^{-2} = 4 \iint \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \sqrt{f(\vec{t})} \right|^2 d\vec{t}. \quad (31)$$

For a symmetric pupil, $A(-\vec{r}) = A(\vec{r})$, the expression between bars in (30) is real, and (31) can be evaluated by means of Parseval's identity, yielding

$$\bar{\sigma}_x^{-2} = 4 F k^2 \iint A(\vec{r}) r_x^2 d\vec{r} = 4 N k^2 \langle r_x^2 \rangle, \quad (32)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ denotes an average over the entrance pupil. The intrinsic imprecision of the diffraction image is thus inversely proportional to the root-mean-square extent of the entrance pupil in the measuring direction. Consider for instance a circular pupil of diameter D , a rectangular pupil of full length L in the x direction, and an interferometer with two small pupils separated a distance W in the x direction. Eq. (32) gives respectively

$$\bar{\sigma}_x = 1.0000 \lambda / (\pi D \sqrt{N}) \quad (\text{circular pupil}) \quad (33)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_x = 0.8660 \lambda / (\pi L \sqrt{N}) \quad (\text{rectangular pupil}) \quad (34)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_x = 0.5000 \lambda / (\pi W \sqrt{N}) \quad (\text{interferometer}) \quad (35)$$

To reach the theoretical limit $\bar{\sigma}_x$ requires in general that the position $\vec{t}$ of each photoelectron is known, i.e. that we possess an ideal, two-dimensional photon-counting detector. While such detectors already exist (e.g. the Image Photon Counting System⁽²⁶⁾), they do not yet have sufficient positional stability and linearity for astrometric work over any appreciable angle. Photoelectric astrometry must then rely on some kind of modulating device, followed by a detector having little or no spatial resolution. It is of the greatest interest to study the theoretical capabilities of such modulators. For simplicity, consider only the circular pupil for which (30) becomes the Airy function

$$f(\vec{t}) = \frac{N}{\pi} \left(\frac{J_1(kDt/2)}{t} \right)^2. \quad (36)$$

The variance (6) is easily evaluated for this image profile, assuming Poissonian noise and different weighting functions. It is found that the mean errors of the trimmed mean (16), trimmed median (17), and rotating knife-edge (twice the mean error of the trimmed median) are all minimized if they are confined to a circle of radius $a = 1.22 \lambda/D$, i.e. the radius of the

first minimum of the Airy function. Without trimming ($\alpha = \infty$), the mean is in fact inconsistent, i.e. it does not converge to a definite point as $N \rightarrow \infty$. This is because the Airy function tapers off too slowly for large values of t . In eq. (6) this is manifested by the divergence of the upper integral. The median is still consistent for $\alpha = \infty$, but gives a 6.5 % larger mean error than with $\alpha = 1.22 \lambda/D$.

The entry in Table 1, "astrometry satellite", refers to the modulation technique envisaged for the presently studied European space astrometry project.⁽²⁷⁾ It is supposed that the accuracy will be set by diffraction and photoelectron noise for the fainter stars observed ($> 9^m$). Modulation is achieved by means of the spinning motion of the satellite causing star images to move across a grid with a regular pattern of transparent and opaque bands. If the fundamental period of the grid is between λ/D and $2\lambda/D$ radians, there results a sinusoidal intensity variation behind the grid. The modulation factor $M = (f_{\max} - f_{\min}) / (f_{\max} + f_{\min})$ is, for a circular entrance pupil,

$$M = \frac{4}{\pi} \left(\arccos(\lambda/gD) - (\lambda/gD) \sqrt{1 - (\lambda/gD)^2} \right) \frac{\sin(\pi q)}{\pi q} \quad (37)$$

where g is the grid period and qg the width of the transparent bands (q is thus the average transmittance of the grid). We may suppose that an optimal location estimator is used to determine the phase of the modulated signal, so we can apply eq. (11) and find the mean error for a signal containing qN photoelectrons:

$$\sigma = \frac{g}{2\pi} \left(qN (1 - \sqrt{1 - M^2}) \right)^{-1/2} \geq 3.552 \lambda / (\pi D \sqrt{qN}); \quad (38)$$

the minimum mean error is obtained with $g = 2\lambda/D$ and $q = 0.3486$. It must be concluded that the modulating grid, even when optimized for highest accuracy, makes bad use of the astrometric information contained in the diffraction image. Apparently, this is partly due to the bad matching of the grid to the diffraction pattern. The precision can in fact be improved by obscuring a central part of the entrance pupil; this decreases the DC component of the modulated signal, and hence the over-all noise level, without affecting the AC component.

6.4. Seeing image

Most photoelectric astrometry today is however limited by atmospheric effects rather than by photoelectron noise. The dominant effect seems to be "image motion" caused by random phase fluctuations across the entrance pu-

pil of the telescope. Image motion can be regarded as a type of image noise $e(t)$ which is non-Gaussian and highly correlated over large areas of the image, in sharp contrast to the approximately Gaussian and perfectly white Poissonian noise assumed in the preceding sections.

To study the effects of image motion we have computed the functions f and C characterizing the "frozen" seeing image, using the geometrical optics approximation.⁽²⁸⁾ The phase of light entering the telescope, $\phi(\vec{r})$, at a certain instant, is assumed to be a Gaussian random variable with structure function⁽²⁹⁾

$$E[(\phi(\vec{r} + \vec{\rho}) - \phi(\vec{r}))^2] = 6.88 (\rho/r_0)^{5/3}. \tag{39}$$

r_0 , the Fried parameter, measures the correlation length of the phase fluctuations, and hence their strength. Reported values of r_0 fall in the range 5 - 20 cm with a typical average of 10 cm.^(30 - 32)

The instantaneous intensity distribution of the seeing image is given by (30) if a factor $\exp[-i\phi(\vec{r})]$ is introduced in the integrand. Taking the expectation of the resulting expression, we obtain by means of (39) the average image profile for a circular entrance pupil of diameter D :

$$f(\vec{r}) = F \frac{k^2 D^4}{4\pi} \int_0^1 J_0(ktDz) (\text{arc cos } z - z\sqrt{1-z^2}) \times \exp[-3.44 (zD/r_0)^{5/3}] z dz. \tag{40}$$

J_0 is the Bessel function of order zero. Figure 3 shows an example of the profile for a typical set of parameters. It is practically independent of

Figure 3. Average seeing image profile $f(\vec{r})$ according to (40) (dotted line). Parameters: phase correlation length $r_0 = 10$ cm, pupil size $D = 20$ cm, wavelength $\lambda = 550$ nm. The Gaussian core of standard width $0.55''$ contains about 80 % of the integrated intensity. The very extended wings resemble those found in actually observed seeing profiles.^(33, 34)

the pupil diameter D , if this is larger than r_0 .

It is found that the noise covariance function can be written

$$C(\vec{t}_1, \vec{t}_2) = F^2 \left(\frac{k}{4\pi} \right)^4 \iiint G(\vec{h}_1, \vec{h}_2) \exp[-ik(\vec{t}_1 \cdot \vec{h}_1 + \vec{t}_2 \cdot \vec{h}_2)] d\vec{h}_1 d\vec{h}_2 \dots (41)$$

where

$$G(\vec{h}_1, \vec{h}_2) = M(\vec{h}_1) M(\vec{h}_2) \times \iint U(\vec{\Delta}, \vec{h}_1, \vec{\Delta} + \vec{h}_2) \left(\frac{M(\vec{\Delta}) M(\vec{\Delta} + \vec{h}_2 - \vec{h}_1)}{M(\vec{\Delta} - \vec{h}_1) M(\vec{\Delta} + \vec{h}_2)} - 1 \right) d\vec{\Delta}; \quad (42)$$

$$M(h) = \exp[-3.44 (h/r_0)^{5/3}] \quad (43)$$

is the long-exposure atmospheric MTF,⁽³⁵⁾ and

$$U(\vec{a}, \vec{b}, \vec{c}) = \iint A(\vec{r}) A(\vec{r} - \vec{a}) A(\vec{r} - \vec{b}) A(\vec{r} - \vec{c}) d\vec{r} \quad (44)$$

is the overlapping area of four pupil functions centred on $\vec{0}$, $\vec{a}$, $\vec{b}$, and $\vec{c}$.

The numerical evaluation of σ is not a trivial task. The complete expression for the numerator of (6), obtained by inserting eqs. (41) - (44), is a twelvefold integral which cannot be numerically evaluated in this form. It reduces however to a manageable sixfold integral by using an analytical expression for U , representing the weighting function by its Fourier transform, and applying Parseval's identity (note that C is the Fourier transform of G). Thus C is never explicitly calculated. The denominator of (6), and eq. (7) for the optimum weighting function, are similarly transformed.

The last column of Table 1 gives some numerical results for $r_0 = 10$ cm, $D = 20$ cm, and $\lambda = 550$ nm. They agree excellently with the empirical mean error for zero exposure time, 0".42, derived by Hølg.⁽³⁶⁾ Another test is provided by Tatarskii's analytical expression for the standard deviation of the centre of gravity of the seeing image,⁽²⁸⁾ which in terms of the Fried parameter becomes

$$\sigma = 0.412 \lambda r_0^{-5/6} D^{-1/6}, \quad (45)$$

or 0".414 in our case. Fried⁽²⁹⁾ studied image motion by computing the rms wavefront tilt in the entrance pupil; this apparently gives an expression identical to (45) except that the numerical factor is 0.477. It should be noted, finally, that r_0 is not independent of λ ; in fact, in the geometrical optics approximation, $r_0 \propto \lambda^{6/5}$, so that σ is actually independent of λ .

Table 1. Mean errors obtained for different images with different location methods. The first three images are Gaussian (with N events, standard width s) plus background. The fourth image is the Airy pattern for a circular pupil (diameter D , wavelength $\lambda = 2\pi/K$). The fifth is a frozen seeing image ($r_0 = 10$ cm, $D = 20$ cm, $\lambda = 550$ nm). For trimmed estimators the mean errors given are for an optimum cut-off distance α (in brackets []). NA = not applicable.

Type of image	ONE - DIMENSIONAL		TWO - DIMENSIONAL		seeing
	background + Gaussian	background - Gaussian	background + Gaussian	Airy diffraction disk	
$f(t)$	$\frac{N}{\sqrt{2\pi}s} \left[\frac{1}{g} + \exp(-t^2/2s^2) \right]$	$\frac{N}{\sqrt{2\pi}s} \left[\frac{10}{g} - \exp(-t^2/2s^2) \right]$	$\frac{N}{2\pi s^2} \left[\frac{1}{g} + \exp(-t^2/2s^2) \right]$	$\frac{N}{\pi} \left[\int_1^{KDt/2l} \right]^2$	eq. (40)
Noise	Poissonian	Poissonian	Poissonian	Poissonian	eq. (41)
Optimum method	1.237 $s/\sqrt{N}$	1.122 $s/\sqrt{N}$	1.335 $s/\sqrt{N}$	1.000 $\lambda/(\pi D/N)$	0".12
Least-squares fit	1.362 $s/\sqrt{N}$	1.266 $s/\sqrt{N}$	1.491 $s/\sqrt{N}$	—	—
Trimmed mean	1.294 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [2.4 s]	1.488 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [1.3 s]	1.425 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [2.5 s]	1.303 $\lambda/(\pi D/N)$ [1.22 λ/D]	0".14
Trimmed median	1.424 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [2.9 s]	1.261 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [1.6 s]	1.569 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [2.8 s]	1.735 $\lambda/(\pi D/N)$ [1.22 λ/D]	0".46
Rotating knife-edge (constant noise)	(NA)	(NA)	1.412 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [2.8 s]	(NA)	0".17
Rotating knife-edge (variable noise)	(NA)	(NA)	3.138 $s/\sqrt{N}$ [2.6 s]	3.470 $\lambda/(\pi D/N)$ [1.22 λ/D]	—
Astrometry satellite	(NA)	(NA)	(NA)	3.552 $\lambda/(\pi D/N)$	—
Applications	slit micrometer; emission line	absorption line	photographic star image; faint seeing image	space astrometry	bright seeing image

7. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Although the sample images included in Table 1 are too few and specialized to allow more general conclusions to be drawn about the merits of the various location methods, there are a few evident trends and relations worth pointing out.

It is hardly surprising that the relative precisions of the different estimators depend on which kind of image we have. Compare for instance the mean and the median: for locating the one-dimensional "emission" feature the mean is the better estimator, while the median should be preferred for the "absorption" feature. This particular difference is clearly an effect of the assumed Poissonian nature of the noise (variance increasing with signal), since the two images would be equivalent if the noise variance was independent of the signal. This also accounts for the 10 % larger mean errors obtained with the unweighted least-squares fit, compared with the optimum methods. A least-squares fit with correct statistical weighting (i.e. a minimum- χ^2 fit) is essentially a maximum likelihood estimator and hence optimal. Correct statistical weighting is obviously equally important for cross-correlation methods.

The most striking results are perhaps those obtained for the diffraction image. The modulating techniques (the rotating knife-edge and the grid of the astrometry satellite) turn out to have quite low efficiencies, about 8 % in terms of the number of photons effectively used. Even the quadrant detector (trimmed median) is far from optimal with its 33 % efficiency. It seems that good efficiency in this case can only be reached with a spatially resolving photon-counting detector followed by a rather elaborate signal analysis.

The case is radically different for the seeing image. Of the methods investigated, only the median gives a slight loss of precision compared with the optimum method. This demonstrates the very dominating nature of image motion for absolute ground-based optical astrometry: once the frozen seeing image is displaced from its average position, this cannot be retrieved even by the most sophisticated analysis of the image.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I wish to thank Prof. G. Larsson-Leander and Dr. D. Dravins of Lund Observatory for numerous helpful comments and discussions.

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Discussion:

H.K.Eichhorn asked where the weighting functions came from. Were they chosen by the physics of the apparatus or arbitrarily, and, if the latter, what is their physical or geometrical justification?

L.Lindegren replied that, in the case of the rotating knife-edge, for instance, the weighting function is determined by the shape of the rotating aperture and by the type of demodulation square-wave and cosine demodulation give slightly different weighting functions. If the weighting function is implemented in the computer, it can be given any desired shape.

E.Høg inquired if it would be possible to devise a weighting function which avoided magnitude equation in a sli micrometer where the star image may be slightly asymmetrical, perhaps on account of coma. He felt that the median would be particularly favourable in this case.

L.Lindegren answered that this was probable true because the median gives not too much weight to the outermost parts of the image where the effects of aberration are relatively more important. He did not know exactly what the optimum weighting function for this case would be, but it could no doubt be computed.